

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

A descriptive study on the search trends between dental treatment and toothache home remedy during the COVID-19 pandemic

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ABSTRACT

Background: Google Trends (GT) can be used to investigate the search trends of oral health-seeking behavior. This study aimed to show the search trends of Filipinos for dental treatment and toothache home remedies from 2020 until 2022. **Methods:** Using GT, search parameters using the keywords “dental treatment” and “toothache home remedy”, the Philippines as country, 2020-2022 for time range, health as category, and web search as the database was made. **Results:** The search trends showed that the highest peak of interest for toothache home remedies was 100% in March 2020. The search for toothache home remedies was more throughout the time range. However, the search for dental treatment gained more popularity last September 2021 at 74%. **Discussion:** In comparison to toothache home remedies, dental treatment searches in the Philippines from 2020 to 2022 are considerably lower during the COVID-19 pandemic. **Conclusions:** Filipinos were more interested in searching online for toothache home remedies than dental treatment.

Keywords home remedies, toothache, treatment, COVID-19, oral health

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1 | Introduction

The outbreak of COVID-19 has caused the closure of dental clinics globally wherein even patient access to emergency dental care was limited. This was due to the risk of infection

associated with Aerosol Generating Procedures (AGP), such as high-speed drill usage.¹ At the time when re-opening of dental clinics was allowed, safety guidelines were implemented. These guidelines stressed the need to focus on minimizing staff, patient, and public risk of infection as well as supporting high-quality dental care. Wherein recommendations on patient triage system and emphasis that only

emergency and urgent dental care should be addressed, usage of class 2 facemasks, reduce risk of transmission, and avoidance of AGP are to be done.² The implementation of these recommendations in conventional dentistry may have resulted in a considerable financial burden for dental practitioners compromising their capacity to remain financially stable due to the needed investment to ensure that they are fit to comply with the specific COVID-19 considerations. And as a result, the cost of conventional dentistry has increased dramatically causing patients to be less capable of affording dental treatments, especially those who are less fortunate and had become unemployed during the height of the COVID-19 lockdown. Due to the inaccessibility to dental treatments and lockdown restrictions, people who had toothache had no other choice but to look for alternatives or other solutions to treat their pain. According to Pavitra, et.al., people would rather do home remedies to treat their toothache rather than leave their home and seek emergency dental care.³

Dental pain is common in all age groups, this hinders us from performing daily activities like eating, sleeping, drinking and many more. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) 80% of the world's population relied on traditional herbal

medicines for their health needs. Because of the pandemic there were higher self-perceived dental pain and the long duration of suffering of these individuals has affected their Oral Health related quality of life. Clove was commonly used as a home remedy to relieve pain, second would be the use of warm saline, other remedies included use of crushed garlic, steam and cold compression. Since many dental clinics were closed during the lockdown, the percentage for people using home remedies has abruptly increased during this period.⁴

According to Dziarnowska and Stankiewicz, due to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic the queries about "dentist" has decreased during the lockdown and followed by an increase in "toothache" search after the lockdown or in the post pandemic period. Google trends can be used as a tool to collect data on the internet, it can show significant changes in queries for dental-related terms during the COVID 19 pandemic.⁵

This study compared public interest between conventional dental treatments and toothache home remedies during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study aimed to determine the Google search trends of Filipinos for toothache home remedies and dental treatments between the years 2020-2022.

Figure 1. Interest over time of the searches for dental treatment versus toothache home remedy from 2020-2022 of Filipinos.

2 | Results

2.1. Interest over time

The interest of Filipino people in dental treatment is less compared to toothache home remedies from 2020-2022. The highest internet search for dental treatment was on September 12, 2021 at 74%, while the highest for toothache home remedy was on March 29, 2020 at 100%.

The interest of the Filipino people for dental treatment was non-existent (0%) on January 05, 2020, but increased to 23% on January 12, 2020 just days after the lack of interest. The highest search interest was on

September 12, 2021 at 74% and at 11% on July 31, 2022.

The interest of the Filipino people for toothache home remedy gained interest on January 05, 2020 at 17%, but had a sudden drop at 0% on February 02, 2020. The highest search interest was on March 29, 2020 at 100% and presently it has dropped to 0% on July 31, 2022 (Figure 1).

2.2 Compared breakdown by sub-region

In terms of the highest searches for dental treatment, the first ranked sub-region was Metro Manila (59%), followed by Central Luzon (54%), Calabarzon (53%), and Central Visayas (34%).

On the other hand, the top sub-regions with the highest searches for toothache home remedy are Western Visayas (100%), Davao Region (100%), Northern Mindanao (100%), Central Visayas (66%), and Calabarzon (47%) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Compared breakdown by sub-regions in the Philippines for the searches of dental treatment versus toothache home remedy from 2020-2022.

3 | Discussion

In this study, the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) reporting guideline was used to facilitate proper discussion of the results. (<https://bit.ly/3AK88w5>)

The majority of Filipinos would still seek toothache home remedies. According to the results from 2020 to 2022 in Figure 1, there was already high interest in toothache home remedies prior to the COVID-19 lockdown.⁶ And upon implementation of the said lockdown, there has been a

continuous increase in the number of internet users searching for toothache home remedies and dental treatment information over the years (Figure 1). These trends are consistent among different regions in the Philippines; the first ranked sub-region was Metro Manila, followed by Central Luzon, Calabarzon, and Central Visayas (Figure 2). Most of the time, the Internet is used as a guide to self-treat toothache by taking medication and/or home remedies especially during the COVID-19 pandemic period.

The priority of a dentist is to eradicate pain with several dental procedures but this was limited when the first case of SARS-CoV-2 arrived in the Philippines in January 2020 when 2 Chinese nationals took a vacation. Due to a lack of personal protective equipment (PPE) to assist flatten the curve and safeguard patients and dental staff from infection during the initial wave of the pandemic, routine dental services were restricted. The first wave's widespread disruption in the delivery of dental treatment may have had significant repercussions on dentists, other medical professionals, and the general population. Ever since, the cases of dental home remedies have spiked to a 100% when COVID-19 made its peak in March 2020, when lockdown was implemented in the entire Philippines. Abdelrahman et al., have displayed in their study that there were greater impacts in the private

sector than in the non-private sector as most dentists have reported practice closure because of COVID-19. Factors at the professional, practice, and national levels were linked to closure.⁷

Home remedies were popular even back then before the COVID-19 lockdown, these remedies were popular to a population who have low economic status and do not have any access to professional care. According to a study written by Jaiswal, et. al, people with low socio-economic status rely on self-medication by buying over-the-counter drugs and doing home remedies to relieve their pain since they do not have access to professional care that can manage their oral health problems.⁸ Even before, the extensive usage of home remedy is attributed to confidence in the remedy, ease of use and access, not enough time to seek professional help, cultural beliefs, low socioeconomic status, relatively high cost of modern medicines, side effects, and interactions of pharmacological treatment and lack of oral health care awareness in many areas of the country. According to Nasseh et.al, poor people who do not have any insurance are hindered from seeking professional dental care treatment.⁹

Over the course of the restriction measures, the populations that were already more accustomed to searching for information about dental treatment and toothache home

remedies on the Internet increased this activity. According to Rizzato et al., measures of social limitation were linked to preferences in digital information about toothaches.¹⁰ These findings enable the identification of the dental needs of different populations, assisting in the planning of focused public health strategies both during and after the pandemic. Most recently, Działowska et al., found that greater dental needs in the post-pandemic period are predicted by a decline in "dentist" queries during lockdown followed by an increase in "toothache" searches. The monitoring indicates that during the COVID-19 pandemic, there were considerable changes in the terms used to search for dental-related terms.⁵ Mahmudi et al., demonstrated that compared in the last four years the interest in toothache and tooth pain has significantly increased. This simply implies the relevance of dental care as urgent medical care worldwide. Government spending on oral health and urban populations are among the key factors for controlling the population's online toothache care behavior.¹¹ The social restrictions and pandemic state brought about changes and new demands for the general populace, including the scenario of universalized fear and uncertainty prior to the disease, related psychosocial burden, changes in routine and daily habits, socioeconomic impacts, decrease in

family income, and financial crisis.¹² These variables may cause people to change their schedules, which may result in neglect of medical and dental care. The pandemic has made the treatment of orofacial pain more difficult to manage than ever before. With this, routine dental care is occasionally delayed, and patients may address emergencies using alternatives that are not strongly recommended.

According to the results in Figure 2, most urbanized areas/regions showed more interest in dental treatment compared to those in the rural regions. Findings revealed that the interest for dental treatment among the rural population in the Philippines is alarmingly low which means that people in rural areas are more likely to utilize home remedies to alleviate dental pain and other oral health problems. Older people in rural areas still adhere to their beliefs and traditions to alleviate the pain of toothache, particularly in the areas that cannot be reached by dentists. Because their fees are minimal to the services of quack doctors/dentists and faith healers are still sought.¹³ This large disparity between dental treatment interest of rural and urban areas is very evident in the study that we conducted. Such disparity can be attributable to financial and non-financial barriers. Financial limitations experienced by people in rural areas

especially during the start of the COVID-19 lockdown is one of the reasons why the interest for dental treatment in such a population is very low. Study conducted by Dalanon et al., conveyed that the income of a population is a strong indicator of their willingness to pay (WTP).¹⁴ WTP is a key factor in assessing the type of healthcare preference that a certain type of population will choose.¹³ The study that was conducted December 2018, discovered that Cebuano mother's monthly WTP for dental treatment services was low. In a similar study a group of researchers stated that an average family of four earns PHP 23, 376.92 or USD445. Of that amount, PHP18, 806.60 or USD358 has already been allocated to monthly expenditures. A meager amount of PHP4, 570.32 or USD87 is left for savings of for other expenses.¹⁵ Hence, even before the start of COVID-19 most of the income of a regular Filipino is already too low for them to even consider having a dental treatment service and during the start of the COVID-19 lockdown this restriction in their budget was heavily affected to the point where they were already having difficulty in meeting even their most basic household needs.¹⁶ This financial shortfall that's being faced by most of the Filipino population especially those in the rural areas is one of the contributory factor why the search for toothache home remedy is

relatively high compared to dental treatment.

Non-financial factors that also contributed to the rural-urban disparity (RUD) include but are not limited to accessibility, distribution of oral health services, oral health knowledge and practices, and prevalence of oral diseases.¹⁷ According to Somkotra et al., even with universal health coverage, inequality and inequity in oral healthcare utilization still exist. The poor are more likely to access and utilize services at subsidized public facilities, particularly community hospitals, as opposed to the wealthier who tend to utilize services at private facilities.¹⁸ Accessibility to oral healthcare services can be closely associated with a population's socioeconomic status. The limited accessibility to dental services in remote and rural areas may contribute to the urbanization disparity in dental service interest. The distribution and availability of healthcare services also play a big role in the decision-making of the population on whether to choose dental treatment services or to patronize toothache home remedies. Rural areas are often associated with low education levels, which are related to low levels of health literacy and poor use of healthcare services.¹⁹ Not all studies have found associations between oral health literacy and dental utilization²⁰; however, many studies

have reported that increased oral health literacy is associated with improved oral health status.²¹ Lower oral health literacy may have also accounted for the rural-urban difference in dental service interest. Health literacy is a known mediator between socio-economic factors, health behavior, and oral health outcomes in various populations, explaining gradients in oral health status and outcomes.²² All of these non-financial barriers are somewhat connected to one another. Accessibility can be greatly affected by the distribution of oral healthcare services. If accessibility and availability of dental services are low, oral healthcare knowledge/literacy will most likely be also low and if oral health knowledge/literacy is low then there will be a higher prevalence of oral diseases. All of the things mentioned are examples of RUD in the utilization of oral healthcare services that contributed to the less interest in dental treatment of those people in rural areas.

In the recent months of 2022 shown in Figure 1, the interest in dental treatments is greater than toothache home remedies. This may be because of the nationwide free COVID-19 vaccination and the removal of the tight restrictions in the whole country wherein it has allowed the public to feel safer to receive medical and dental care. Many individuals

believe that the risk of disease transmission such as COVID-19 in dental clinics is low.²³ But majority of those who actually seek dental care post-pandemic are those who have a stable income, where they can allocate expenses for dental care, and are part of the younger population.²⁴ Because a lot of older individuals still believe that they are susceptible to contract COVID-19 in dental clinics causing them to be cautious to whether receive dental care.²⁵ Even though they were one of those sectors in the population who were prioritized to received free COVID-19 vaccination, they are still fearful of the possibility of having COVID-19 this may be due to their health problems and/or low immune system function. Another possible reason for this is that access to information and updates related to COVID-19 are usually found in different social media portals and most older individuals are having a hard time navigating it. Findings showed that the highest search for dental treatment during early months of 2022 did not reach 100%. Personal financial conditions, lack of awareness, and fear of contracting COVID-19 due to improper or unclear knowledge of guidelines stated by local authorities or WHO were identified as important contributory factors for the general public's interest to return for professional dental care.²⁶ With the changes brought to us by the pandemic

and with digitalization and social distancing being the new normal, its effects on the psychosocial aspect of the population should be given great consideration.

The researchers cannot confirm that all searches typed into google have been made by people with toothaches seeking dental care or home remedies for relief. However, according to Lotto et al., the lack of media influence on the time series and the direct association between primary searches and endodontic pain self-management indicated that searches were primarily conducted by people interested in resolving toothache.²⁷ Furthermore, Google accounts with all specific queries within a specific time range come from different Protocols hence there's overestimation of the interest in dental treatment and home remedies due to the potential for double searches. In addition, other factors could explain the sudden increase of dental treatment and toothache home remedies queries. Xiong et al., demonstrated in their study the impact of COVID-19 ranges from increased stress, heightened loneliness and increasing mental health difficulties.²⁸

4 | Methods

4.1. Data acquisition

Google Trends website was used to compare the terms “toothache home remedy” and “dental treatment” were

used. Google Trends website was accessed on August 13, 2022 at 1:00 pm. Philippines was chosen as the country but focused more on seven sub-regions namely, Metro Manila, Central Luzon, Calabarzon, Central Visayas, Cordillera Administrative Region, Davao Region, and Northern Mindanao. Time range observed was from 2020 to 2022. Category is under Health and web search as a database.

4.2. Statistical analysis

A descriptive analysis was done using the graphic representation of the comparison between toothache home remedy vs dental treatment in Google Trends. The results were shown in percentages and presented in either a line graph or a color intensity map.

5| Conclusions

The Filipinos were more interested in searching online for toothache home remedies than dental treatment during the COVID-19 pandemic particularly when lockdowns were implemented. In January 2020, prior to COVID-19 lockdown, searches for toothache home remedies were already high and had peaked in March 2020 with the start of COVID-19 lockdown. But when restrictions started to loosen, the interest in dental treatment started to rise in contrast to the interest in toothache home remedy. Dentists can utilize Google Trends to investigate Filipinos' preferences or search

patterns concerning their dental health. This can help policymakers encourage proper oral hygiene and seek out reputable healthcare providers rather than treat toothaches with home remedies, which cannot be guaranteed to be safe and effective.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, R.B., J.A.R., C.E.V.; Methodology, R.B., J.A.R., A.A., R.G.; Validation, R.B., J.A.R., Resources, R.B., J.A.R., C.E.V., A.A., J.C., R.G.; Writing-Original Draft, R.B., J.A.R., C.E.V., A.A., J.C., R.G.; Writing-Review & Editing, R.B., J.A.R.

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Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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